

D2.1 COMMUNICATION PLAN

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1. Executive Summary

This communication and dissemination plan ensures that the results of CLS INFRA are exploited across all appropriate user communities.

These communication and dissemination activities will not be limited by geography and will address Computational Literary Studies (CLS) and Digital Humanities (DH) communities worldwide because the outcomes of CLS INFRA can realistically aspire to create infrastructures for scholars and citizen scientists that are multilingual, interconnected, and international.

The strategic CLS INFRA communication plan will be established with our broad target communities in mind, and will build an offline and online presence for the project with the aim to:

- Disseminate the project goals and outcomes effectively;
- Roll out efficient tools for communication with different stakeholders (online and offline);
- Build a vibrant community of stakeholders that will assist in expanding the project's reach to underrepresented constituencies;
- Exploit the synergies in liaisons and collaborations with other infrastructures and groups;
- Recruit new users across all levels of expertise;
- Publicise and promote CLS INFRA events.

As target-orientated and efficient communications need to be strategic, accessible, integrated, and participative, suitable measures will be planned and implemented to realise the strategic development of our communications strategy in order to ensure the identified image of CLS INFRA is reaching its target audiences.

The current communication and dissemination plan (v1.0) is based on the project aims and objectives initially articulated in the Grant Proposal and has been adapted and extended accordingly. We anticipate changes and updates to this plan over the course of this project's development; these are and will be summarised in the Document History section of the document's front matter.

V1.1: Significant changes to this document are reflected under each heading that has received them. An appendix of revisions undertaken to form version 2.1 is contained at the end of the document.

2. WHY: Introduction and Background - Analysis of the Situation

Human beings are storytellers and fictional world makers, and nowhere do we see the expression of human ambitions, values, norms, and desires more clearly than in the collected literary works that have been created over the centuries of documented human creativity.

Literary texts are cultural artefacts and historical documents, but they may also be viewed as sources of data. Recent years have seen increasing dialogue within the growing community of research users focussed on creating and using literary data. With this growing discourse, we can now see what, precisely, is required to enable investigations into the multilingual and interconnected European literary heritage. Understanding this essential part of our shared and varied cultural heritage is key for understanding and enhancing our rich, complex, interconnected, and pluralistic European identity.

Efforts across Europe to expand, digitise, and make literary heritage legally and practically accessible have been made since before the dawn of the internet. However, the landscape of digital literary sources remains fragmented to this day: scholars and lay readers alike struggle to find texts that are made accessible and reusable in standardised ways, with some regions, eras, and languages enjoying far better coverage than others.

This landscape of standalone literary corpora and isolated resources for computational analysis is increasingly recognised as a major stumbling block for the development of pan-European Computational Literary Studies (CLS).

Attempts to remedy this situation in Europe were driven by the activities of key networks such as COST Action 16204, “Distant Reading for European Literary History.” Established in 2017, this project aims to create a vibrant and diverse network of researchers jointly developing the resources (including ELTeC, a multilingual European Literary Text Collection) and methods (establishing and sharing best practices and develop innovative computational methods of text

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analysis adapted to Europe's multilingual literary traditions) necessary to change the way European literary history is written. Along with other projects such as the ERC-funded POSTDATA project for poetry and the DraCor corpus collection of European Drama, CLS INFRA aims to build upon the background of CLS in Europe.

The overall aim of CLS INFRA is to create unified and easy access to the best European and national infrastructures for the CLS community which has not been fully supported to benefit from the existing infrastructures and data resources. The CLS community is a growing community that requires tools and services customized with a specific focus on literary data (including narrative prose, poetry and drama) from large ESFRI research infrastructures like DARIAH and CLARIN, as well as a common and easy access to the literary data from scattered national infrastructures to reflect the literary and cultural diversity of Europe. To unleash the excellent research potential of the CLS community, this project is essential for engaging a larger number of literary researchers, especially young researchers and researchers with disadvantaged backgrounds, to use the existing infrastructure and data for CLS.

The project will therefore consolidate, integrate, and further develop institutional, national, and regional efforts to build shared and sustainable access to the high-quality data, tools, and knowledge in the field of literary studies, in general, and Computational Literary Studies, in particular.

CLS INFRA will build a sustainable and shared infrastructure for CLS. It will build upon existing European and national infrastructures to significantly reconfigure access paradigms for literary data, vastly improving its adherence to the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) principles, and enhancing tools for extracting, disseminating, and documenting literary works within the constraints of existing copyright laws. In addition, it will seek to develop new tools and services for CLS users: it will integrate and optimise existing tools and services for the CLS community, including in the domain of Natural Language Processing (NLP), in order to build, share and sustain robust, reusable and standards-compliant workflows for CLS. The participation of DARIAH ERIC as well as key DARIAH and CLARIN partners in the CLS INFRA Consortium will guarantee the uptake of the project results within the respective communities.

The project also aims to create the necessary conditions for the wider adoption of digital technologies in traditional literary studies and other related disciplines. CLS INFRA will map

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user requirements specific to the CLS community and implement a tactical infrastructure as an ecosystem of API-enabled “Programmable Corpora” in order to bridge the gap between their requirements for effective, easy access and the realities of fragmented, protected, distinctive resources. It will deepen, widen and consolidate the user base for CLS sources and methods by providing support services and training for using established and emerging cutting-edge methodologies; building user-friendly components to facilitate participation of users from underrepresented regions and languages; and analysing non-academic user needs for future development. Throughout its activities, the project will aim to establish sustainable networks and nodes of shared infrastructural practices to institutionalise and sustain training and scholarly exchange in order to enable systematic and meaningful cooperation between disciplines, communities, countries, and languages.

3. HOW: Determination of the Targets

3.1 Overall Objectives

The overall aim of the CLS INFRA project is to create unified and easy access to the best European and national infrastructures for the Computational Literary Studies (CLS) community which has not been fully supported to benefit from the existing infrastructures and data resources. The project will therefore consolidate, integrate and further develop institutional, national and regional efforts to build shared and sustainable access to the high-quality data, tools, and knowledge in the field of literary studies, in general, and CLS, in particular.

To achieve this overall aim, CLS INFRA will pursue the following specific objectives, expressed in a refinement of the initial projections. These have been reviewed for V2.3 with changes noted.

3.1.1 Objective 1

Bridging knowledge-based resources for CLS community: Build on existing European and national infrastructures to significantly reconfigure access paradigms for literary data (including narrative prose, poetry, and drama), vastly improving its adherence to the FAIR (findable,

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accessible, interoperable, reusable) principles, and enhancing tools for extracting, disseminating, and documenting literary works within the constraints of existing copyright laws.

OBJECTIVE 1 Bridging knowledge-based resources for CLS community		
Target Outcome	Indicator	Target
Publication of reports on existing resources in CLS	Completed reviews of ecosystems for literary data (D5.1), inventory of existing data sources and formats (D6.1), programmable corpora (D7.1), APIs and corpora (D7.3, 7.4), NLP tools and processes (D8.1, 8.2)	10 reports
Scientific output on knowledge-based resources for CLS	Number of scientific journal articles Number of scientific conference papers / posters	3 articles 3 papers/posters

Table 1: Objective 1 (3.1.1)

3.1.2 Objective 2

Mapping and matching specific requirements of CLS community: Map user requirements specific to the CLS community and implement a tactical infrastructure as an ecosystem of API-enabled “Programmable Corpora” to bridge the gap between their requirements for effective, easy access and the realities of fragmented, protected, distinctive resources.

OBJECTIVE 2 Mapping and matching specific requirements of CLS community		
Target Outcome	Indicator	Target
Publication of reports on present and future of CLS	Completed reviews of baseline methodological needs of CLS users (D3.1), skills matrix and gap analysis (D4.1), and roadmap for the future of CLS (D1.2)	3 reports

Scientific output on key methodological concerns of CLS	Number of survey papers on key methodological concerns	5 papers
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Table 2: Objective 2 (3.1.2)

3.1.3 Objective 3

Developing new digital tools and services for CLS users: Integrate and optimise existing tools and services for the CLS community, including in the domain of Natural Language Processing (NLP), in order to build, share and sustain robust, reusable and standards-compliant workflows for CLS.

OBJECTIVE 3 Developing new digital tools and services for CLS users		
Target Outcomes	Indicator	Target
Use of transformation tools	Endorsement expressed by assigning stars and/or forking the code of the transformation toolbox on GitHub (D6.2)	$\geq 20^*$ This code will be published in M48. This target refers to the end of the project reporting period.
	Endorsement expressed by by downloads of (D6.3) report.	≥ 45
Use of API libraries	Numbers of stars and forks on GitHub. Number of users on API logs. Usage statistics of the python library will be tracked on https://libraries.io/pypi/pydrac or; R on CRAN or similar service (D7.2)	≥ 20
Use of NLP resources	Number of users of Named Entities-extraction pipeline (D8.3) Number of users of entity-relation-extraction prototype (D8.4)	≤ 10 users (not satisfactory) ≥ 10 users (satisfactory) *Deadline for D8.4 and D8.5 is M48. Therefore this target refers to total users until final reporting period.

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	Number of users of sentiment analysis pipeline (D8.5)	
Resources for data sharing	Completion of toolkit report for data sharing between researchers and institutions (D5.3)	1 report
Scientific output on development of digital tools and services for CLS	Number of scientific journal articles	3 articles
	Number of scientific conference papers / posters	3 papers/posters

Table 3: Objective 3 (3.1.3)

3.1.4 Objective 4

Mainstreaming of new digital tools/services: Deepen, widen and consolidate the user base for CLS sources and methods by providing support services and training for using established and emerging cutting-edge methodologies; building user-friendly components to facilitate participation of users from underrepresented regions and languages; and analysing non-academic user needs for future development.

Significant changes in v2.1: Online training materials are hosted at DARIAH CAMPUS, with some videos of training schools available on the CLS INFRA YouTube channel, the educational websites of other institutions such as UNED's CANAL site, and as other materials such as an interactive grid that forms part of D3.2 hosted on the CLS INFRA website. Per DARIAH advice, the targets for accessing such materials are reduced significantly (from 500 to 250 at M24 and 2000 to 500 at M48). As of February 2024, DARIAH CAMPUS users of materials from two training schools are estimated in the low 20s, with 38 viewers of the TS:Madrid archival videos on CLS INFRA and an estimated 150 viewers of the interactive grid.

OBJECTIVE 4 Mainstreaming of new digital tools/services		
Deliverable	Target Outcome	Target
Use of online training	Number of users by M24	<= 500 (not satisfactory)

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materials	Number of users by M48	>= 500 (satisfactory) <= 2000 (not satisfactory) >= 2000 (satisfactory)
Attendance at training events	Number of registrations per event	<= 40 (not satisfactory) >= 40 (satisfactory)
Attendance at community-building and satellite events. In particular we are interested in connecting with the ADHO Special Interest Groups: https://adho.org/special-interest-groups-sigs	Number of CLS INFRA Team members presenting or facilitating at these events by M48	<= 100 (not satisfactory) >= 100 (satisfactory)
Publications on CLS research	Completion of showcases of CLS research accompanied by explanatory papers (D3.3) and case studies in data preparation and sharing (D5.2)	4 showcases & papers 3 case studies
Publications on emerging trends in CLS	Number of position papers and pilot studies on emerging trends in CLS (D3.4)	3 position papers 2 pilot studies

Table 4: Objective 4 (3.1.4)

3.1.5 Objective 5

Strengthening a culture of cooperation: Establish sustainable networks and nodes of shared infrastructural practices to institutionalise and sustain training and scholarly exchange in order to enable systematic and meaningful cooperation between disciplines, communities, countries and languages.

Significant changes in v2.1:

The Training Schools in Prague (2022) and Madrid (2023) resulted in evaluative reports that provide useful information on reaching and connecting our audiences to form effective cooperative networks. Thus in v2.1 we add a target of three such reports.

As Twitter / X lost popularity and fragmented into many social media communities in 2023, increases in the number of CLS INFRA followers slowed significantly. Responding to this, CLS INFRA started a Mastodon account in March 2023. In conjunction with outreach materials that

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target non-academic users, a social media push in 2024 will significantly expand into the social media spheres of cultural / historical institutions and citizen science. Similarly, CLS INFRA will monitor and explore other social media channels as the communities there build. Thus target audience numbers were reduced in v2.1 from 3000 to 2000.

As resources and other content is added to the CLS INFRA website the number of visits increases. However, CLS INFRA publicity and communication channels necessarily point to other sites such as DARIAH CAMPUS and Sciences Call for two key audiences: Potential Training School attendees and potential TNA fellows and their mentors. In addition, some reports, tool interfaces, and other CLS INFRA deliverables are necessarily linked to more permanent hosting on, for example, Zenodo and DraCor. Thus website engagement targets are reduced from 500 to 400 in v2.1.

OBJECTIVE 5 Strengthening a culture of cooperation		
Deliverable	Target Outcome	Target
Research visits (Transnational Access Programme)	Yearly number of TNA Fellows from M12-M48	7-9
Forming institutional alliance for CLS	Number of institutions in alliance (M48)	14-15
Reporting on user needs beyond academia	Completion of report on user needs beyond academia (D3.5)	1 report
Reporting on CLS training	Completion of final report on training events and materials (D4.2) Evaluative report following each training school.	1 report 3 reports
Reporting on TNA Programme	Completion of final report on TNA Programme, including process documentation and impact analysis (D9.1)	1 report
Reporting on communication and dissemination	Completion of final report on dissemination,	1 report

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	communication, and exploitation (D2.2)	
Social media engagement	Number of followers / subscribers (M48)	<= 2,000 (not satisfactory) >= 2,000 (satisfactory)
Website engagement	Creation of a dynamic website that serves as a hub of information for project members and target audiences. Measured by website analytics.	<= 400 visits per month (not satisfactory) >= 400 visits per month (satisfactory)

Table 5: Objective 5 (3.1.5)

3.2 Overall Impact

CLS INFRA is exceptionally well-positioned to deliver high impact results for the community of researchers, across sectors and interests, who use literary sources as a basis for their work. The project will make the data, tools and knowledge for computational literary studies easily and widely accessible in a coordinated and sustainable fashion; sharing standards and other drivers of efficiency and effectiveness across complementary data holders and developers; democratising and lowering the bar for digital approaches in this field, in particular for early career researchers; consolidating the research community; and exploring possible socio-economic benefits of enhanced and integrated access to digital and digitised literary texts.

Building upon the technical backbone, basic assets and experiences of a number of active, but disconnected, infrastructures and projects, CLS INFRA will eventually integrate its results into the DARIAH ERIC in a way that will be a guarantor of long-term sustainability. DARIAH-ERIC, as full partner of the project, has committed to use its extensive network and technical acumen not only to maintain the tools and services developed within the project, but also to meet the challenge of consolidating the community of literary studies and helping it fully embrace the digital as a mode of intellectual engagement with the text. It is, therefore, to be expected that the impact of CLS INFRA will be both technological and social: while the field of computational literary studies is much smaller than that of literary studies in general, our activities aimed at expanding the user base and providing user-friendly tools and workflows will make computational literary studies much easier to enter as a field, even for those researchers with little or no previous experiences in using digital tools.

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The CLS INFRA project will have a significant impact at **four levels of granularity**: that of the individual researcher, the institution, the research policy, and technology and innovation.

3.2.1 Individual Researcher

The primary stakeholders of the CLS INFRA Starting Community for computational literary studies are the researcher users of infrastructures for the digitally-enabled investigation of literature and culture. We have optimised our consortium to deliver for this community in several ways:

Firstly by bringing together key European as well as nationally-based infrastructures and services to further their development at European level, we ensure wider and easier access of the best research infrastructures in Europe to literary researchers, while also giving these institutions and projects the opportunity to draw in return on the diverse, humanities research-led, results of the project generated by the CLS community. In this way, we will greatly expand CLS researchers' access to and awareness of key resources available at a national level, but which may otherwise be hidden to potential users outside of the country where they were developed for reasons of visibility, language of interaction, or politics. Also, we will be working closely on the delivery of the project with the DARIAH ERIC, whose status and continuity will ensure that project results have a wide dissemination and reuse value.

Secondly, a significant theme within our development is a focus on bringing the 'researchers to the tools and the data' physically and especially virtually. Our commitment to the development of accessible training materials and opportunities for learning and mentoring, will align our activities to ensure that we are enabling skills development across the career stages and locations in which literary scholars beginning their engagement with the field of computational literary studies, find themselves. This will allow CLS INFRA to not only broaden its training and transnational access provision over the current baseline, but also to deepen its multiplying impact through nurturing a new generation of researchers.

Thirdly, our support for individual researchers in the time of the grant and beyond will be the best that can be offered. The Transnational Access programme will give at least 36 researchers direct access to some of the highest performing facilities in Europe for computational literary scholarship. The fact that we will recruit strongly among non-established researchers (including

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early stage researchers, researchers in less digitally developed countries, and citizen scientists) will increase the impact of these fellowships. These researchers will also form an important part of the dissemination and communication strategy by creating and sharing research across our platforms and across a diverse range of CLS INFRA's target communities.

Finally, by involving representative researchers in the CLS community directly in the project team, we ensure adherence to a co-created user-centric approach in which real advances for the community can be facilitated by technical development in a rich context of interdisciplinary sharing of knowledge and techniques. Our network of projects and collaborators beyond the project team will also be a significant asset in engaging, and extending, current accepted practices in the domain of computational literary studies.

3.2.2 National/European Infrastructures and Research Institutions

As mentioned above, the CLS INFRA consortium draws its strength from the contributions of key national infrastructures and projects that have so far, for various reasons, achieved a somewhat limited scope or scale. There are 6 tentpole projects as well as a variety of smaller projects that will play a vital role in contributing to the success of CLS INFRA. By bringing these partners together for joint development toward mutually beneficial goals, CLS INFRA will foster harmonisation of data and services across Europe, and reduce duplication in parallel national or project contexts. By facilitating sharing, CLS INFRA will also enable countries with less well-developed national infrastructure to offer access to cutting edge services to their communities (which they would often not be able to invest in on their own) and enable project-level services to achieve larger audiences and enhanced sustainability.

Knowledge based resources, both explicit (collections) and tacit (scientific information and processes that are documented, but almost infinitely adaptable) will be drawn together and integrated effectively for the good of the researchers, but also very much for their institutions. Being able to show a more direct link between their efforts to promote access to such knowledge and the impact it has on the knowledge generation processes of literary scholars will be of great value, both in planning strategically for future developments, but also in making the case for their impact to external stakeholders and funders, and provide cost effective, efficient investment with partners across Europe.

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The CLS INFRA project will provide these institutions with clear and actionable guidance regarding their user engagement directed toward the literary research community. Through the CLS INFRA community and communication mechanisms, they will not only be supported in the improvement of their own services but also access a wider perspective on the research and researchers they support, the policies and practices that are emerging elsewhere in the system (such as open science and the EOSC), and the possible impact multipliers they may be able to access through the methodological and training initiatives CLS INFRA develops or through specific software or processes that will be made openly available through the nascent SSH Open Marketplace for Tools and Services (being developed by DARIAH).

In addition, for those institutions directly or indirectly involved in the training of researchers, CLS INFRA will provide a contextualised and robust set of materials they can use to develop their curricula or support independent learning for their local users, leading to better links between their skills provision and a growing user base of young and/or semi-professional literary scholars.

3.2.3 Research Policy

1. Awareness of and satisfaction with CLS INFRA originating tools, services and initiatives;
2. Strengthened culture of cooperation between institutional, national players and DARIAH;
3. Increased diversity of European literary data resources openly accessible;
4. Increased potential for international cooperation in literary research;
5. Increased potential for cross-disciplinary research informed by easily accessible European literary data.

Facilitating Open Science (e.g. by investing into sustainable research infrastructures, providing for incentives to mobilise new user bases, or regulating for the integration of Open Science principles) is an important issue for EU policy-making. Focusing on literary research, CLS INFRA sets out to make a contribution to informing respective policy discourses and evidence-based policymaking (see e.g. Lee & Kirkpatrick, 2006).

Computational literary studies and, indeed, the humanities in general remain highly marked by the atomised and heterogeneous nature of sources and methods, and the analogue workflows upon which so much of even digitally-enabled humanistic work relies (see for example Edmond

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and Garnett, 2015). As a result, it is not a surprise that reuse of research outputs, even high-profile, publicly available ones, has been generally low. By establishing both a modular, ‘tactical’ (Sheratt, 2015) approach to infrastructure development (so as not to impact on aspects of a process where change is epistemically intrusive) and by placing an emphasis on ensuring an ecosystem by which to increase and harmonise the skills bases of the individual users, CLS INFRA will increase the possibility for reuse of its own results and, by example, of others in the wider ecosystem.

CLS INFRA will produce policy and technology briefs for local, national and EU-level policy makers not only on the topic of sustainability of research results, but also, more generally, on the adoption of open science principles within humanities disciplines (an often challenging matching between emerging, STEM-driven policies, and the practices and values of humanities research communities).

3.2.4 Technology Development and Innovation

CLS INFRA will also inform the emerging debate about cultural innovation (Pozzo, 2017), and how this can be better promoted, or, to turn the question around, how culturally informed perspectives can better inform technical developments, promoting new approaches inspired by challenging cultural content. Because CLS INFRA focuses on literary data and humanistic approaches, it will be in a position to reinforce some of the social and cultural aspects of technological adoption that engineering-led processes can sometimes obscure. Such advances will be enabled by both the critical mass and advancement of both methods and researcher cultures within CLS INFRA. This is only a nascent conversation in the computational literary studies community, but one which CLS INFRA will foster and grow through its activities which will be specifically reaching out to this potential user and stakeholder base.

3.3 Dissemination Activity Impact

In order to create unified and easy access to the best European and national infrastructures for the CLS community which has not been fully supported to benefit from the existing infrastructures and data resources, CLS INFRA will:

- establish and communicate current best practices in methods for the analysis of authorship, author gender, literary genre, and the canon;

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- map, consolidate, and expand the CLS community around current best practices with respect both to datasets and tools used and to methods of analysis employed by researchers in CLS;
- disseminate showcases (for the major literary genres covered) of successful applications of CLS methods to existing datasets which have been produced by infrastructures as well as in projects, by individual researchers and which are harmonized and federated by CLS INFRA;
- define data sharing policies by creating robust documentation and guidelines around clearly defined workflows for producing, describing and annotating literary datasets in accordance with international standards and interoperable formats;
- organise outreach materials, seminars, training schools, and events in order to support new users in the CLS community to engage in dynamic knowledge exchange across national borders, which will be about 1) harmonising access to resources by developing joint conceptual and metadata models for advanced data exchange, large-scale data mining and enhanced discoverability; and 2) preventing a duplication of services by fostering better coordination of activities between national and transnational efforts in the field of literary studies;
- to strengthen the virtual CLS community by providing online training modules (e.g. on literary corpus curation, natural language processing for literary texts, or text mining for literary texts) as Open Education Resources (OER) via DARIAH-Campus, a discovery framework and hosting platform for Digital Humanities training materials;
- produce position papers on emerging trends driving innovation in CLS research;
- demonstrate the usefulness of the principles of the CLS INFRA ecosystem for applications beyond CLS and even beyond academia.

3.4 SWOT Analysis

The structure of the CLS INFRA project leads to a number of unique strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats regarding its communication and dissemination objectives:

The *strengths* of the project are articulated in the large network of partners, involved in existing research infrastructures with their communication channels, rather than the existence of representatives from each target audience within the consortium, the project's long term vision,

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as well as its commitment to providing accessible CLS infrastructure, training, and resources. Because we are building upon an experienced network of nationally embedded partners, not to mention the European flagship DARIAH, we already have a solid basis for recognition of our outputs and engagement with us. We also have a properly resourced Dissemination and Communication function, as well as multiple layers of user engagement to improve fit with user needs.

The *weaknesses*, such as the difficulty of tailoring messages to specific target groups in order to reach audiences beyond academia and the potential difficulty of articulating more technical aspects of computational literary studies in communication activities should likewise be considered.

CLS INFRA offers *opportunities* to support smaller organizations and/or projects and individual researchers whilst developing its own infrastructures across the lifetime of the project. This will benefit our target audiences within and outside of academia and allow us to tailor our deliverables across target communities.

Identified *threats* manifest themselves in the targeted (non-CLS) audiences not being familiar with CLS terminologies and concepts, consequently missing out on communication and participation approaches specifically addressed to them after losing interest in the project rather than not being aware of the project's existence.

Cultural and heritage institutions and organisations might struggle with conveying the applicability of CLS methodologies to their citizen users.

Another threat-issue is addressed in missing (new) output and outcomes due to a non-efficient collaboration with CLS INFRA partners, while they themselves might fail to support the infrastructure's sustainability, by limiting themselves to contributing input but not providing information and tutorials regarding the infrastructure's usability. As a consequence, a non-efficient use of the infrastructure due to a lack of information on how to use it should be considered and is factored into the communication and dissemination plan in terms of internal consortium communications with WP2.

Significant changes in v2.1:

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Through the life of the project new strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats occur.

The CLS INFRA project's success at supporting and linking smaller organisations and projects has attracted significant interest. New *opportunities* are available in closer links with researchers in under-resourced and under-recognised academic communities such as computational literary studies scholars active in Romania.

However, new *threats* have manifested in public concern with the rapid advancement of AI and machine learning applications. Thus we will clearly and transparently communicate the use of these technologies, addressing such concerns as appropriate.

The table below visualizes the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats described above:

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Large network of partners (and their contacts). ● Most partners are involved with existing research infrastructures and communication channels. ● Representatives from user groups are mostly present in the consortium. ● The project's long term vision. ● Provision of accessible infrastructure, training, and resources. ● Dedicated Dissemination and Communications WP. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Tailoring messages to diverse target groups may be difficult. ● Reaching target groups beyond academia may be difficult. Especially considering there is no citizen scientist representation in the consortium. ● Potential for too much focus on technical aspects of CLS in communication activities.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Supporting smaller groups and organisations. ● Building infrastructures that respond to target community needs through collaboration. ● Creating opportunities for CLS methodologies outside of the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Target audiences may not be aware of CLS terminology, methodologies, and concepts. ● Missing output due to non-efficient communication with partners. ● Difficulty for heritage and cultural institutions to convey applicability of

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academy.	CLS to their users. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public concern over AI and machine learning.
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Table 6: SWOT Analysis (3.4)

3.5 Communication and Dissemination Principles

A set of basic principles will ensure that the project's strengths and opportunities are rolled out during its evolution, whilst the above-mentioned weaknesses and threats shall be diminished, managed and faced with awareness.

1. *Adaptability*: Given the scope of the project and the specific themes involved, the communication strategy needs to be comprehensive enough to cover the project as a whole, while being adaptable to other parties and stakeholder communities, which could benefit from the project discoveries, infrastructures and outcomes. For example, specific channels will be used to reach particular target groups, and dissemination materials may have to be tailored to the needs of different end users.
2. *Flexibility*: CLS INFRA's communication through its distribution channels needs to be flexible and open in order to create a responsive framework for being aware of needs and challenges in its attempt to address audiences through its communication activities.
3. *Dynamism*: Adaptability and flexibility combined generate a dynamic element. A dynamic strategy is a key to maximise the impact of CLS INFRA.
4. *Wording*: On the one hand, CLS INFRA speaks to academic users (researchers, students, etc.) in CLS fields as well as the field of Digital Humanities. On the other hand, it addresses cultural and heritage institutions (e.g. public libraries, museums, etc.), industry, and the public at large. Therefore, CLS INFRA will follow a multi-layered communication strategy that uses accessible language with tailored messages (specialised, technical/linguistic vocabulary vs. jargon-free language) to speak to its varied audiences.
5. *Integration*: A key aim of CLS INFRA is to integrate CLS methodologies, infrastructures, and resources across target communities. Our commitment to collaboration across communities and our open-access communication and dissemination commitment will ensure that high levels of integration are achieved across and within target communities.

4. WHO: The Audience - Target Groups

Various types of users and external audiences will benefit from the scalable project outcomes. The project addresses not just a direct audience but also reaches out to intermediaries on a pan-European level. In order to reach different target groups, multi-channel dissemination actions will be carried out, with information adjusted to the level of needs and involvement of the targeted audience.

The most fundamental requirement of this community is for durable, shareable, reliable infrastructure that can be optimised so that standardised and reusable data, tools and protocols can be shared broadly so as to increase the innovation potential of this cohort of scholars. As such, our communications infrastructure intends to create a long lasting home for our outputs to ensure that each target group can access these materials.

Several major target groups have been identified:

4.1 Target Group 1: Academic Researchers

The direct target group of training activities and tools/services developed in the CLS INFRA project is literary scholars (digital and analogue). They will be reached through our corpora, training events, publications, conference papers and dissemination materials. Beyond that, other humanities scholars who use literary sources, interdisciplinary scholars looking at cultural norms and values (for example in challenge-based settings, looking at democratic participation, sustainable lifestyles, etc.), and also technical researchers and information scientists at every career stage will also be actively reached through multiplier and dissemination events.

4.2 Target Group 2: Institutions

Universities, research centres and institutes, cultural heritage institutions, e-infrastructures, learned societies and academies with interest in literary and cultural research. While some of the institutions are already directly involved in and through project activities, the institutions will be further classified for targeted outreach activities in the long-run, especially using dissemination materials, data sharing policy, and reports.

4.3 Target Group 3: Policy Makers

European and national agencies and government departments involved in higher education research and innovation, training and skills; European and national research funders. A targeted group of policymakers will be directly engaged in advisory and dissemination events, while the rest will be regularly informed of the project activities with dissemination materials such as the project Newsletter. In addition, policy briefs will be developed and disseminated via all channels.

4.4 Target Group 4: Industry

In particular, technology and creative industries, but also cultural heritage, education, journalism and tourism. Relevant non-academic partners will be engaged through training and advisory activities directly or indirectly through dissemination activities and materials such as infographics and mailing lists.

4.5 Target Group 5: Citizens and Other Kinds of Researchers

Life-long learners, citizen scientists, non-academic researchers, journalists, genealogists, educators, tourism professionals. These individuals interested in accessing the literary data and methods made openly accessible by the project will be reached through mass media or social networks of other stakeholders directly engaged in the project during and after its period of funded activity.

The following table summarises the communication policies that CLS INFRA participants will undertake in correspondence to the target audience:

Target Group	Description/Example	Dissemination Approach	Activities/Channels
Target Group 1: Academic Researchers			
CLS Researchers	These researchers will already have a background in using computational literary studies methods but will benefit from this	This group will be interested in sharing resources, collaborating with project members, and attending	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website - Social media - Mailing lists - Newsletter - Transnational Access

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	project's infrastructures.	<p>project events to upskill.</p> <p>Dissemination in this group will focus on upgrading their CLS use, creating opportunities for collaboration, and providing training on new infrastructures.</p>	<p>Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scientific papers/dissemination. - Targeted workshops and research events. - Online training courses or training measures.
Literary Scholars	These scholars will work in the field of literary studies but will have limited or no background in CLS methodologies.	<p>This group will be interested in developing awareness and skills in CLS methods and will require guidance on how these methods could apply to their own fields of research.</p> <p>Dissemination in this group will focus on demystifying CLS and creating accessible, entry level training outputs that will enhance their learning and approach.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website - Social media - Mailing lists - Newsletter - Transnational Access Activities - Scientific papers/dissemination. - Targeted workshops and research events. - Online training courses or training measures.
Humanities Scholars	These scholars will work in the humanities more broadly and be interested in CLS methods to further their own research.	This group will be interested in developing interdisciplinary connections with colleagues and will be interested in developing awareness and skills in CLS methods and will	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website - Social media - Mailing lists - Newsletter - Transnational Access Activities - Scientific papers/dissemination. - Targeted

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		<p>require guidance on how these methods could apply to their own fields of research.</p> <p>Dissemination in this group will focus on demystifying CLS and creating accessible, entry level training outputs that will enhance their learning and approach.</p>	<p>workshops and research events.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Online training courses or training measures.
Target Group 2: Institutions			
Higher Education Institutions	<p>Consortium institutions.</p> <p>Digital humanities departments.</p> <p>Humanities departments.</p>	<p>These groups will have varying knowledge of or interest in CLS, comprising researchers from the three groups listed (left).</p> <p>Dissemination approaches will thus be mixed, addressed to different levels of attention and interest.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website - Social media - Mailing lists - Newsletter - Infographics, publicity material - Transnational Access Activities - Scientific papers/dissemination. - Targeted workshops and research events. - Online training courses or training measures.
Research Institutes	<p>Research Institutes</p> <p>Research Societies</p> <p>Organisations and</p>	<p>As above, these groups will have varying knowledge of or interest in CLS, comprising</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website - Social media - Mailing lists - Newsletter - Brochures,

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	networks of consortium members	<p>researchers from the three groups of academic researchers.</p> <p>Again, mixed dissemination methods will be used.</p>	<p>publicity material</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transnational Access Activities - Scientific papers/dissemination. - Targeted workshops and research events. - Online training courses or training measures.
Heritage Institutions	<p>Museums</p> <p>Libraries</p> <p>Archives</p>	<p>Scope for communicating existing or potential collaborations: with CLS INFRA using existing GLAM resources, or with GLAM institutions using new CLS corpora and tools. Individual institutions could be approached for partnerships.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website - Social media - Direct communication / community building. - Targeted workshops and research events. - Online training courses or training measures.
Cultural Institutions	<p>Learned societies</p> <p>Public libraries</p> <p>Citizen groups</p>	<p>Similar scope for communicating existing or potential collaboration. Individual institutions could be approached for partnerships.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website - Social media - Direct communication / community building. - Targeted workshops and research events. - Online training courses or training measures

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Target Group 3: Policy Makers			
Policy-Making Agencies	<p>European government actors: Commission (eg. DG RTD A4; D3/D4, REA) MEPs (members of ITRE, CULT), DG CNCT, DG EAC</p> <p>EU-level Agencies/Lobby groups: Science Europe, EASSH, CESAR, University associations</p> <p>National Research Funders and Ministries in partner countries</p> <p>National Agencies and Lobby Groups (Open Science, Humanities)</p>	Scope for communicating about the sustainability of research results, and on on the adoption of open science principles within humanities disciplines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website - Social media - White papers and Reports. - Targeted workshops and research events. - Policy briefs - Mapping of individual interests and personal contacts (email, phone call)
Target Group 4: Industry			
Technological and Creative Sectors	<p>Technology</p> <p>Creative Industries</p>	Non-academic groups which may enable the project outputs and aims to access a more mainstream user community.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website - Social media - Direct communication / community building. - Brochures, publicity material. - Targeted workshops and research events. - Online training courses or training measures
Broader Social and	Heritage	Non-academic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website

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Cultural Sectors	Cultural Education Journalism	groups which may enable the project outputs and aims to access a more mainstream user community. Additional scope for media communication of project outputs and aims.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social media - Direct communication / community building. - Brochures, publicity material. - Targeted workshops and research events. - Online training courses or training measures
Target Group 5: Citizens and Other Kinds of Researchers			
Citizen Scientists and other kinds of Researchers	Non-academic Researchers Life-long learners Educators Journalists	This group may be targeted through the promotion of access to the literary data and methods made openly accessible by the project, and with communications activities tailored for more public audiences.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website - Social media - Mass media - Brochures, publicity materials.

Table 7: Target Groups (4.5)

5. WHAT: The Tailored Message

CLS INFRA will use its networking activities to create knowledge about and interventions toward addressing skills and competency gaps of potential users of computational methods in literary studies, defined as widely as our capacity allows, from the most limited applications in tool use to the widest implications of humanities modelling, datafication, and visualisation.

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Training school topics and workshops have been chosen to respond to D4.1 Skills Matrix and Gap Analysis, using this report to determine most under-served areas of training. Participants are chosen to be at an intermediate level of skill with basic CLS tools and concepts such as Python and Stylometry methods, based on self-reported skill levels.

5.1 General Message

The general message represents the official definition of the project, displayed on the project's website (www.clsinfra.io) and will be used on official dissemination materials:

The overall aim of CLS INFRA, a European Commission-funded project, is to create unified and easy access to the best European and national infrastructures for the Computational Literary Studies community. This includes: connecting the building of resources and infrastructure, providing training environments and networks, and promoting the theoretical considerations of these resources and infrastructures.

5.2 Message for Target Group 1: Academic Researchers

The key points of interest for this group are:

- Bridging knowledge-based resources for CLS community
- Developing new digital tools and services for CLS users
- Mainstreaming of new digital tools/services
- Strengthening a culture of cooperation: Establish sustainable networks and nodes of shared infrastructural practices to institutionalise and sustain training and scholarly exchange.

On the one hand, academic researchers are encouraged to use the infrastructure provided, on the other hand they will be encouraged to *collaborate and mainstream* the infrastructure to create new networks and resources. Special attention will be given to academic researchers in marginalised groups.

The message for this target group will be to promote ease of access and to demystify CLS methods in order to create a wider user base for the use and development of CLS infrastructures.

5.3 Message for Target Group 2: Institutions

The key points of interest for this group (as well as the above) is:

- Mainstreaming of new digital tools and services: Deepen, widen and consolidate the user base

These institutions (consisting of partner institutions, research institutions, higher education institutions) are an influential group and can assist with the mainstreaming of these new digital tools and services. Their cooperation will encourage increased usership across all target groups and will thus widen the user base.

The message for this target group will be to promote the infrastructural, interdisciplinary, and service opportunities emerging from this project and to encourage their cooperation in mainstreaming the project's outputs.

5.4 Message for Target Group 3: Policy Makers

CLS INFRA will produce policy and technology briefs for local, national and EU-level policy makers not only on the topic of sustainability of research results, but also, more generally, on the adoption of open science principles within humanities disciplines (an often challenging match between emerging, STEM-driven policies, and the practices and values of humanities research communities).

In order to make CLS INFRA's outcomes as easy as possible for policy makers and potential industry collaborators to absorb, our key findings will be released in addition as policy and technology briefs or white papers, targeted at the information needs and channels of local, national and EU-level policymakers and of industry leaders. Drawing on the overall work, development and findings of CLS INFRA, WPs 2 and 3 will prepare and disseminate regular policy and technology briefs that will inform policy discourse in relation to sustainability and Open Science, and elaborate on the HE/industry cooperation in the areas of Digital Humanities and research infrastructures. Over the course of the three cycles of direct interaction, we are honing our method of interacting with industry, a largely unexplored field for humanities research infrastructure. The policy and technology briefs as well as the information about the

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workshops will also be made available on the project website. Infographics will be used to communicate concepts and tools concisely.

5.5 Message for Target Group 4: Industry

This target group (in particular technology and creative industries, but also cultural heritage, education, journalism and tourism) are an important group for the project as their position outside of the academy will allow for the project outputs and aims to access a more mainstream user community.

The message for this target group will be to promote training and advisory activities that will allow for non-academic users to access, gain confidence, and contribute to CLS infrastructures and methods.

5.6 Message for Target Group 5: Citizens and Other Kinds of Researchers

These life-long learners, citizen scientists, non-academic researchers, journalists, genealogists, educators, and tourism professionals. This group will be targeted through the promotion of access to the literary data and methods made openly accessible by the project and will be reached through mass media or social networks of other stakeholders directly engaged in the project during and after the project.

6. WHEN: Multi-level Communication

One of the main challenges for CLS INFRA's communication and dissemination strategy is how to appropriately and effectively engage with all of its stakeholder communities and target groups. Because CLS INFRA aims to develop a unique balance between the imperatives of professional research and those of citizen science it is essential that the project's communication and dissemination activities satisfy the needs of professional and research communities as well as communicating to the public in an understandable and "jargon-free" fashion.

The way in which the audiences shall be addressed (online and offline) varies, depending on the target group:

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- Researchers, Project Leaders and Infrastructure professionals will be addressed in an educational, informative, institutional way. Online and in digital communications, the adequate target-oriented wording should be enriched for example with videos and photos in order to attract attention.
 - The types of communication will be wide-ranging. For example: academic papers at conferences and in journals, training activities (summer/winter schools, on-line modules, and curricula), and reference and training materials.
- Stakeholders in Infrastructure and Institutions will also be addressed in an educational, informative, institutional way, with communications to this community focusing on reports and presentations that address the needs of and tap into the networks of institutions and providers of e-infrastructural services, making them aware of the policy work CLS INFRA is undertaking toward the development of more open and efficient provision for literary and historical research.
- For Policy Makers and Industry we will draw on the overall work, development and findings of CLS INFRA. WPs 2 and 3 will prepare and disseminate regular policy and technology briefs that will inform policy discourse in relation to sustainability, Open Science and elaborate on HE/industry cooperation in the areas of Digital Humanities and research infrastructures. Over the course of the three cycles of direct interaction, we would hope to be able to hone our method of interacting with industry, a largely unexplored field for humanities research infrastructure. The policy and technology briefs as well as the information about the workshops will also be made available on the project website.
- We anticipate that these public audiences will be opened up through our regular communications via the electronic media and popular media which will lend themselves well to communication with the general public. For individuals with a less casual interest in our work, white papers will be written with the intention of making our contribution to a wider dialogue about human capacity and competency in building accessible infrastructures.

As all online and offline communication and dissemination activities aim to create awareness about and interest in the CLS INFRA project, all communications platforms (social media, website, etc.) will aim to be connected in their output whilst providing specific information, addressing different audiences of interest (this is more specifically laid out in Section 7 below).

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In order to interact and communicate with the different target groups, different communication tools will be adopted, used, and tailored for the specific platform and audience. Furthermore, calls-to-action will be initiated, e.g. grants for research visits and TNA fellowships, to encourage researchers to participate and optimise mutual knowledge exchange and to strengthen the social layer of the CLS INFRA infrastructure.

7. WHERE: Communication Channels

As each project partner is committed to create a high level of publicity for the project right from the beginning, the launch and objectives of CLS INFRA will and are being communicated through partners' communication channels (e.g. press releases, newsletters, news-related media, website, social media etc.) - to generate broad public awareness of CLS INFRA activities.

Nevertheless, CLS INFRA is also establishing its own communication channels, to bundle partner activities and produce its own output, whilst *collaborating* with its partners to foster community building by generating awareness (online and offline) and stimulate participation.

CLS INFRA can count on a variety of available (communication) channels and resources (listed below in Table 8), that are managed either by CLS INFRA, CLS INFRA Consortium partners or third parties. It is important not only to use our own channels and resources but also third party channels in order to raise the project's reach. The list is not exhaustive and will be expanded during the lifetime of CLS INFRA.

Type	CLS INFRA - Channels	CLS INFRA - Partner Channels	Third Party Channels
Twitter	@CLSinfra https://twitter.com/clsinfra?lang=en	University of Galway: - Twitter: @uniofgalway - Website: University of Galway TCDH (Trier): @CDHTrier	Journal of Computational Literary Studies: @jcls_io Priority Programme CLS: @spp_cls COST Action "Distant Reading": @DistantReading

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		<p>Charles University:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CNC: @Korpus_cz - LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ: @LindatClariahCZ - @matfyz - @FF_CUNI <p>Polish Academy of Sciences:</p> <p>@pan_akademia</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Instytut Języka Polskiego PAN: @IJP_PAN <p>University of Potsdam:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - @unipotsdam - @dh_potsdam <p>Austrian Academy of Sciences:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - @oeaw - @ACDH-OeAW <p>National University of Distance Education:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - @UNED <p>École Normale Supérieure de Lyon:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - @ENSdeLyon <p>Humboldt University of Berlin:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - @HumboldtUni <p>Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - @DARIAHeu <p>Ghent Centre for Digital Humanities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - @GhentCDH <p>Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences:</p>	<p>CzADH: @CzADH</p> <p>DH Krakow initiative: @dhkrakow</p> <p>Digital Repository of Ireland: @dri_ireland</p> <p>CLARIN: @CLARINERIC</p>
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		- @_knew	
Mastodon	@CLSinfra@fedihum.org	<p>University of Galway: @universityofgalway@mastodon.ie</p> <p>University of Potsdam: @dh_potsdam@hcommons.social @unipotsdam@wisskomm.social</p> <p>Austrian Academy of Sciences: @ACDHCH_OeAW@fedihum.org</p> <p>TCDH (Trier):@tcdh@fedihum.org</p>	<p>Service Centre for Digital Humanities, SCDH Münster: @scdh@fedihum.org</p> <p>Associazione Italiana per l'Informatica Umanistica e la Cultura Digitale, AIUCD: @aiucd@fedihum.org</p> <p>Digital Methods Initiative: @dmi@mastodon.digitalmethods.org</p> <p>DH Research Hub: @dh_ResearchHub@hcommons.social</p>
Website	https://clsinfra.io	<p>University of Galway: https://UniversityofGalway.ie</p> <p>Moore Institute: - Website: https://mooreinstitut.e.ie</p> <p>TCDH (Trier): https://tcdh.uni-trier.de</p> <p>Charles University: - CNC: https://korpuz.cz - CUNI: https://ufal.mff.cuni.cz</p> <p>Polish Academy of Sciences: - https://www.ijp.pan.pl/en/</p>	<p>Priority Programme CLS: https://dfg-spp-cls.github.io/</p> <p>Journal of Computational Literary Studies: jcsli.io</p> <p>COST Action “Distant Reading”: https://distant-reading.net https://www.czadh.cz/</p> <p>DARIAH: https://dariah.eu</p> <p>CLARIN: https://clarin.eu</p>

		<p>University of Potsdam:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://www.uni-potsdam.de/en/university-of-potsdam <p>Austrian Academy of Sciences:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://www.oeaw.ac.at/oesterreichische-akademie-der-wissenschaften <p>National University of Distance Education:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://www.uned.es/universidad/inicio.html <p>École Normale Supérieure de Lyon:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - http://www.ens-lyon.fr <p>Humboldt University of Berlin:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://www.hu-berlin.de <p>Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://www.dariah.eu <p>Ghent Centre for Digital Humanities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://www.ghentcdh.ugent.be <p>Belgrade Centre for Digital Humanities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - http://www.humanistika.org <p>Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://www.knaw.nl 	
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		/en/about-us	
YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCxGckuzByS1NVO-BnBePmOg		
Email	info@clsinfra.io		
Mailing List			<p>COST Action “Distant Reading”: MC list (internal)</p> <p>eadh-topics@lists.digitalhumanities.org</p> <p>newsflash@clarin.eu.</p> <p>Humanist discussion group mail to humanist@dhumanist.org</p> <p>AIUCD-L mailing list - Associazione per l'Informatica Umanistica e la Cultura Digitale, IT aiucd-l@lists.digitalhumanities.org</p> <p>DHBenelux mailing list - dh-benelux-mailinglist@googlegroups.com</p> <p>DhD Mailing List: DHd@mailman.rz.uni-hamburg.de</p> <p>DHSI - Victoria University, CA - institute@lists.uvic.ca</p> <p>TEI-L english mailing list - text encoding initiative, US - TEI-L-</p>

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			<p>request@LISTSERV.BROWN.EDU</p> <p>Dariah-be@lists.ugent.be - Dariah BE mailing list</p> <p>eblida-list@sympa.kaapeli.fi (European Bureau of Library, information & Documentation Associations mailing list</p> <p>UK Arts and Humanities Research Council 'translating cultures' list: TRANSLATINGCULTURES-request@jiscmail.ac.uk</p> <p>(Archives in the UK/ Republic of Ireland & AI): AHRC/ IRC Digital Humanities Research Network: AURA-request@jiscmail.ac.uk</p> <p>GLAM wikimedia lists: glam@lists.wikimedia.org, open-glam@lists.wikimedia.org</p>
Newsletter	https://clsinfra.io/contact/		

Table 8: Communication Channels (7)

7.1 Website

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A website (<https://clsinfra.io>), has been created and is hosted by PAS and maintained by the University of Galway, on behalf of the Consortium. The CLS INFRA website is the central pillar of the CLS INFRA communication and dissemination strategy.

This website will serve as the main hub for all CLS INFRA stakeholder communities and anyone else interested in CLS INFRA. It will provide information on the project, links to project tools and resources, activities and events, opportunities, and will serve to augment networking opportunities across the project. As well as directly hosting a wealth of dynamic content that will constantly grow, it will also link to relevant content stored elsewhere, for example publications in repositories, databases, and archives, etc.

The website will serve as a central access point for information on CLS INFRA, its background, aims, and results, as well as providing an access point for its tools, services, and data.

An overview of upcoming CLS INFRA events will be hosted on the 'Events' section of the site, informing interested users of event details and providing them with information on how to register for and attend these events. The 'Events' section of the site will also archive information (including video recordings and publications emerging from) past events to serve as an informative archiving of the project events and associated materials.

The project website will be maintained as a static resource for at least five years after the close of the project, at which point it will be folded into the DARIAH Literary Studies Domain Centre. The website was built using a well-known modular web content manager system (Wordpress), which allows the pages to be fully responsive on all devices (desktop, tablet, and smartphone) and browsers. Figure 1 visualizes the design of the CLS INFRA homepage.

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Figure 1: CLS INFRA website homepage

7.2 Internal Communications Platform

Mattermost (an open source collaboration platform) is CLS INFRA's main internal communication platform (access to our communication channels restricted to group members). This platform allows for secure, quick, and intuitive communications across WPs, members, and project activities and aligns with the project's commitment to open source technology and resources. Email is still used to duplicate some Mattermost posts to those who prefer a single contact source for their communications.

NextCloud is the project's platform for sharing internal documents and files. It is available to the consortium and associated partners and to the European Commission. This platform will be permanently updated and improved in line with the project results. NextCloud is also an open source platform and continues our commitment to open source technology and resources.

PAS is the host for both of these platforms.

7.3 Social Media

In order to generate awareness for CLS INFRA and engage with the targeted audiences and support dissemination activities, the project will be present on several social media networks. The main goal of using social media is to significantly expand CLS INFRA's organic reach, as well as to keep each account up to date by curating continuous postings and shares on a regular basis.

A key strength of the CLS INFRA proposal is its commitment to create a critical mass of coordinated key infrastructure partners, but also to build on current and past initiatives and projects. As a result of this, we will be able to use our social media channels to forge connections and links to these partners and increase our reach through their follow bases. In particular, Twitter / X, Mastodon@fedihum server and YouTube are the main channels of communication.

7.3.1 Twitter

A [Twitter](#) account has been set up, which is used to report on the project's activities, provide electronic news and information gathering on outcomes of events (such as live blogging sessions), and milestones. Twitter's character-based format allows for discursive output as well as the sharing of image and video-based content. It will be used to link to other social networks (such as our YouTube channel), our website, and other relevant events. Its "thread" structure will be useful in collecting and collating groups of publications, videos, resources, and events, and the "pinned" section will be kept up to date with the latest project events and activities. In 2022/2023, changes to the structure and management functions of Twitter (now X) have lessened its efficacy. To broaden our discursive community, WP2 now also posts to a targeted CLS and GLAM audience from the Mastodon@fedihum server. WP2 continues to monitor the location of our targeted audiences on various platforms.

7.3.2 YouTube

A [YouTube channel](#) has been set up, providing interested users with informative videos, e.g. tutorials and training materials on how to use the provided infrastructure, recordings of online or hybrid events, and interview material with group members, partners, and collaborators. This material will be shared across our social media platforms and embedded into our website.

YouTube can also be integrated with a wide range of online meeting and event hosting softwares and this may provide an overflow for online, live events. In addition, links from repositories of materials such as DARIAH-Campus to the CLS INFRA YouTube channel will ensure that branding is consistent across Training School archives, TNA Fellow and Training School attendee interviews, and deliverable explainer videos.

7.4 Email

An email-address (info@clsinfra.io) will be set up which will be used for sending out newsletters and mailing lists and will be used on social media channels in their contact section, to enable the interested user to ask questions or send feedback.

7.4.1 Mailing Lists

A database of up-to-date contacts will be available in order to reach the largest audience possible, who will be regularly updated, filtered by audience, using a (GDPR compliant) mass mailing online tool, such as Mailchimp.

As CLS INFRA members will be present at (project relevant) events, interested recipients will be invited to subscribe to the CLS INFRA mailing list and there will be a subscribe button on the project website.

7.4.2 Newsletter

A newsletter template will be set up according to the CLS INFRA corporate identity guidelines; subscribers will be updated regularly, filtered by audience (for example: early career researchers, citizen scientists, heritage groups, etc.). As CLS INFRA members will be present at (project relevant) events, interested recipients will be invited to subscribe to the newsletter and there will be a subscribe button on the project website.

7.5 Events

Organising, promoting and attending events fosters the community, supports networking with other initiatives/infrastructures, and creates an opportunity to engage with academia, heritage and cultural groups, and the general public. Furthermore it generates dissemination output (e.g. papers in conference proceedings).

These events will be significant reputation-builders across a variety of our audiences. These events will be focused, but also highly interactive, harnessing formats like the world café and the rapid ideation session where appropriate. They will also be recorded and promoted on the CLS INFRA website, to increase their impact.

Information on upcoming CLS INFRA events will be publicised on our website and outputs from those events will also be hosted and promoted through our website and social media platforms. Recordings (where applicable) and outcomes from past events will also be archived on our

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website so that users can engage with the project's activities and events at any stage. Project members can promote and add event information and outputs through the established WP2 communication channels.

During current global restrictions related to the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, it is important to have a strategy for engaging the desired CLS INFRA communities using accessible digital technologies. As such, CLS INFRA is dedicated to an open, accessible, and, where possible, hybrid approach, which will ensure that the widest cohort of our target communities can access our events and activities. We anticipate that online video platforms such as Zoom will be an important tool for our online events in the immediate future and across the life of this project. We also commit to (where appropriate) recording or archiving events and activities to ensure accessibility across communities.

7.5.1 CLS INFRA Events

A kick-off meeting took place on March 15th 2021 and another public-facing meeting will be organised for early 2022, taking place in the first year of the project. In the second, third and fourth year of the project, CLS community-fostering events, such as training schools, will be initiated in order to strengthen the community by encouraging personal contact. The nature of these events will be determined by ongoing COVID-19 travel restrictions and all consortium members will adhere to local guidelines for travel. The annual community events will be organised by the consortium, and hosted by different consortium members. Virtual Meeting Platforms will be used to facilitate these events if necessary.

7.5.2 CLS INFRA Training Measures

CLS INFRA will offer both face-to-face and asynchronous training materials (modelled after the units of the PARTHENOS Training Suite, see: <https://training.parthenos-project.eu/> and hosted on DARIAH-Campus, <https://campus.dariah.eu/>), adaptable to the level and specific needs of a large number of new and semi-established users of CLS methods. In addition, the Transnational Access Fellowships will allow intermediate users to make significant progress on their own specific projects, working in situ with the assets and expertise of their host institutions.

7.5.3 CLS INFRA TNA Fellowships

The Trans National Access Programme will facilitate the invitation of scholars to visit consortium institutions for a spell of 1-3 months to work on tasks or projects related to CLS INFRA. A call for Transnational Access Fellows will be made early in this project (M8) and an external advisory board will be appointed to decide on the successful applicants. The first fellowships are due to begin before or on M13. WP2 intends to utilise these opportunities for dissemination, communication, and impact by spotlighting these Fellows on our website and in other relevant communications materials. As well as this, we intend to create a stipulation that each Fellow would contribute a short blog post, report, video, presentation, publication or social media output during their time in role in order to disseminate their research and training experience. A TNA Archive containing this material on the CLS INFRA website was completed in 2023. A minimum of 12 videos will be completed.

7.5.4 Third Party or Joint Events

Dissemination will be carried out at third party events or joint events (e.g. workshops, conferences, panels, presence at other international or national events) in order to reach out to other communities and enlarge the community of interest. Individual researchers or research groups will aim to participate with posters, panels, or presentations and will present specific project results.

Event Title	(Sub)Field / Audience	Frequency
<i>e.g. ADHO Conference</i>	<i>e.g. Digital Humanities</i>	<i>e.g. Annual</i>
Conference organized by the <i>Journal of Computational Literary Studies</i>	Computational Literary Studies	Annual (Next edition June 2024 in Vienna) (https://jcls.io/site/conference/)
Digital Humanities Benelux Conference	Digital Humanities	Annual (next edition June 2024 in Leuven) (https://dhbenelux.org/)
DHNB Conference (Digital Humanities in the Nordic and Baltic Countries)	Digital Humanities	Annual (next edition May 2024 in Reykjavik) (https://dhnbeu/conferences/)

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DHd Conference (Digital Humanities im deutschsprachigen Raum)	Digital Humanities	Annual (next edition March 2024, Passau)
DHA2021 (Australasian Association for Digital Humanities)	Digital Humanities	Bi-Annual (next edition November 2025, location TBA)
Francophone Association of Digital Humanities (Humanistica)	Digital Humanities	Annual (next edition May 2024, Meknel)
RED de Humanidades Digitales	Digital Humanities	Annual (no information on next edition)
International Conference of Digital Archives and Digital Humanities	Digital Humanities	Annual (next edition December 2021, Changua City, Taiwan)
Full Stack Feminism	Feminist Digital Humanities	Annual, project ended. Attended 2023.
Reimagining Annotation	Multimodal Digital Humanities	Feb 2024, Rennes
UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association	Digital Humanities	Annual (next edition June 2024, Cork) (https://digitalhumanities-uk-ie.org/news-events/)

Table 9: Third Party or Joint Events (7.5.4)

7.5.5 Transnational Access Activities

Over the lifetime of the CLS INFRA project, the consortium intends to arrange a series of Transnational Access Activities. These activities will allow project members and target communities to interact with experts; receive advice on ongoing projects; learn how to use the CLS INFRA ecosystem of data, tools and standards; assemble new literary corpora and bring them to the baseline of the project; contribute additional resources, whether datasets or tools, to the CLS INFRA ecosystem by connecting them to the research pipelines developed within the project. TNA Fellows will be expected to contribute to a set of specific communications activities, to be defined by WP2. Seminars and workshops given by TNA Fellows during or

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about their fellowship are recorded where appropriate, hosted on the CLS INFRA YouTube channel, and linked to the CLS INFRA website and social media channels.

7.6 Dissemination Material

The dissemination material distributed will follow the corporate design guidelines described below. Afterwards, an overview of online and offline distribution items will be given.

7.6.1 Logo and Visual Style

The CLS INFRA logos (figures 2-17) were created by Allen Creative Ltd. for CLS INFRA and were the starting point for creating a visual style for the project.

Within CLS INFRA, we use typography to sustain our image and identity. CLS INFRA's primary typeface is Gotham font, which should be used for professionally designed publications and documents designed by graphic designers. When Gotham is not available, the alternative safe font Arial should be used for official email and Word communications sent by CLS INFRA.

The CLS INFRA colour scheme is designed with two primary and four secondary colours which will allow for a consistent and recognisable aesthetic across all communication channels and publications.

Figure 2: Icon Square Logo Black

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Figure 3: Icon Square Logo Colour

Figure 4: Square Logo Rev Black

Figure 5: Square Logo Rev Colour

Figure 6: Linear Logo Long Black

Figure 7: Linear Logo Long Colour

Figure 8: Linear Logo Long Rev Black

Figure 9: Linear Logo Long Rev Colour=====576999

Figure 10: Short Main Logo Black

Figure 11: Short Main Logo Colour

Figure 12: Short Main Logo Rev Colour

Figure 13: Short Main Logo Rev Black

Figure 14: Stacked Long Logo Black

Figure 15: Stacked Long Logo Colour

Figure 16: Stacked Long Logo Rev Black

Figure 17: Stacked Long Logo Rev Colour

7.6.2 Online Promotion Material

Digital and online marketing activities will be undertaken, which will be styled and branded in relation to the guidelines listed above. These activities will include but are not limited to:

- Regular *news items* in the CLS INFRA *newsletter*, linked to the CLS INFRA *website*;
- Regular *social media posts* on our social media channels (Twitter/X, Mastodon, YouTube) by the project on the CLS INFRA account and by the Consortium members on their institutional accounts or private accounts, including videos, pictures, figures, photos, tables, etc.
- As *videos* are the most shared content on the web, self-produced videos will be shared and posted on social media (Twitter, YouTube); those videos will provide information

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about the deployment of the infrastructure, mini-interviews with experts from the field, mini- tutorials, as well as hints & tips videos for usability in various scenarios;

- Pictures, photo material interactive tools, a library collection, and graphics representative for the project will be generated and distributed through the project's channels
- The project will be present on research portals, *linking to the CLS INFRA website*

7.6.3 Offline Promotion Material

We anticipate that the majority of our promotional materials will be digital, however CLS INFRA intends to utilise print publicity, where appropriate, to maximise the impact of the dissemination activity and to establish an initial contact with organisations where digital marketing proves unsuccessful.

Relevant leaflets, flyers, posters, and other materials will be designed with an option for physical printing in mind and we will also make use of tangible merchandise such as stickers, badges, and stationary for in-person events as necessary.

Print materials will also be available for download from the website (e.g. general info brochure, topic specific one-page inserts, flyers, posters).

8. Scientific Dissemination

Papers and articles about the project results will be published in open access journals and conferences. The online repository *Zenodo* (<https://zenodo.org/>) will be used to preserve peer-reviewed scientific papers and other research materials published by CLS INFRA partners. In 2023, an interactive tool based on D3.2 Survey of Methods was published on the CLS INFRA website, linking to the published papers on Zenodo. A Zotero Collection, or set of bibliographic data on all CLS INFRA publications and presentations, was linked to the website in 2023.

In particular, we will ensure where possible project outputs are available via 'green' open access, either through the repositories of one of the project partners or through the DARIAH

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shared resource repository, HAL. Green Open Access is the norm for humanities publishing but does require educated choices regarding target journals so as to avoid undue delays due to embargos. The leadership of WP2 will consider this issue, carefully, in consultation with project colleagues. Where open access publication is not possible, project members will commit to putting appropriate drafts or pre-publication materials on Zenodo or on the e-Print archive <https://arxiv.org/>.

9. Evaluation, Monitoring and Reporting

The impact created through the innovations implemented in the creation of CLS infrastructures will be measured, as well as the data gathered from training measures (number of participants, etc.). The *outreach and engagement* will be measured with the help of the reporting system of the mass mailing tool, with website analytics (Mailchimp, Wordpress) and with the standard reporting features of social media portals and the figures/data collected at events.

Our communication and dissemination strategy will be kept updated regularly in line with our monitoring and evaluation procedures. The final communication report (M48) will contain summative reflections on communication and dissemination activities, and will also include scientific publications and a collection of digital and non-digital media clippings.

10. References

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1. Appendix: Changes in V2.1

3.1.1 Objective 1	Added 3 additional reports. Revised measurement period for tools to post M48 and before final reporting, and reduced target as most tools will not be available before M48.
3.1.3 Objective 3	Clarified type of targets for use of transformation tools and extending the measurement period to post M48, before final reporting.
3.1.4 Objective 4	Clarified targets for support services in the form of community-building to reflect CLS INFRA team members bringing instruction or facilitation to these events. Revised targets for usage of online training materials to reflect more realistic usage.
3.1.5 Objective 5	Revised table targets based on a review of similar projects and current engagement. Changes not expressed in the narrative include a reduction in TNA Fellows from 8-10/year to 7-9/year and an increase in institutional partners from 14-15. These are based on TNA applications from rounds 1-5 and partnerships current or considered in 2023.
3.4: SWOT analysis	New opportunities and threats identified and included in the appropriate table. COVID-related threats have been minimised and thus removed from the document.
4: WHO: The audience	More closely linked means of dissemination to specific audience groups.
6: WHEN: Multi-level Communication	Added infographics as directed method of communication and indicated progress on other modes such as policy briefs.
7: WHERE: Communication Channels	Updates to table 8 to include Mastodon, expand Twitter / X links, and
7.2: Internal Communications Platform	Verifies use of email in conjunction with Mattermost.
7.3: Social Media	Indicates expansion from Twitter / X into Mastodon social media channels, use of branding across videos on YouTube.

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7.5 Events	Adds details about TNA archive and TNA videos. Adds target number of videos.
7.6 Dissemination Materials	Revises main channels of news dissemination. Adds useful contributions to deliverable dissemination that appear on the CLS INFRA website such as an interactive tool to engage users in exploring D3.2 (Survey of Methods) and a library of publications and presentations.